

Errors which Lead Riemann to Falsely Believe that the Zeta Function Has Zeros

Armando M. Evangelista Jr.

March 01, 2026
arman781973@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: This short work will show the errors in Riemann's 1859 paper[1] which lead him to falsely believe that the zeta function has zeros.

Introduction

Consider the contour integral

$$\int_C \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz$$

where $z = x + yi$ is the independent variable, and $s = \sigma + ti$ is a complex constant. The contour integral depends on s , the endpoints z_1 and z_2 , and the chosen path itself.

For example: if $z = x$, $dz = dx$, $z_1 = 0$ and $z_2 = \infty$, then

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{(-x)^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx = (-1)^{s-1} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx = (-1)^{s-1} \Gamma(s) \zeta(s) \quad \Re(s) > 1$$

where

$$\Gamma(s) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} x^{s-1} dx \quad \text{and} \quad \zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}$$

If $z_1 = z_2$, then we have a closed path, and the integral must be taken over *one* closed path and not over many closed paths.

Riemann's Errors

Error 1 :
$$2 \sin(\pi s) \Gamma(s) \zeta(s) = i \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(-x)^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx \quad (1)$$

For this case: $z = x$, $dz = dx$, and $z_1 = z_2 = \infty$, then

$$i \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = i \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(-x)^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx = i(-1)^{s-1} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{x^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx + \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx \right\}$$

$$= i(-1)^{s-1} [-\Gamma(s)\zeta(s) + \Gamma(s)\zeta(s)] = 0,$$

and so

$$i \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(-x)^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx = 0 \neq 2 \sin(\pi s) \Gamma(s) \zeta(s).$$

Therefore, (1) is an invalid equation.

$$\mathbf{Error\ 2 :} \quad i \int_C \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = (2\pi)^s \sum_{n=1}^N n^{s-1} ((-i)^{s-1} + i^{s-1}) = 2(2\pi)^s \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \zeta(1-s) \quad (2)$$

By applying the Residue Theorem, the contour integral is taken in the negative sense through an infinitely large modulus that encloses all its poles with the real part of s being negative

$$i \int_C \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = i \left\{ (-2\pi i)(0)^{s-1} + (-2\pi i)(2\pi)^{s-1} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{s-1} ((-i)^{s-1} + i^{s-1}) \right\} = \text{undefined},$$

and so

$$i \int_C \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = \text{undefined} \neq 2(2\pi)^s \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \zeta(1-s) \quad \Re(s) < 0.$$

Therefore, (2) is not a valid equation.

By equating these two errors:

$$2 \sin(\pi s) \Gamma(s) \zeta(s) = 2(2\pi)^s \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \zeta(1-s),$$

Riemann obtained his *invalid* functional equation

$$\zeta(s) = 2^s \pi^{s-1} \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \Gamma(1-s) \zeta(1-s).$$

From this invalid equation comes the so-called *trivial* zeroes of $\zeta(s)$ for $s = -2n, n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$ Since Riemann's functional equation is not valid, $\zeta(s) = \text{undefined}$ for $s = -n, n = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$

Error 3:
$$\pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{s(s-1)} + \int_1^{\infty} \psi(x) \left(x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} + x^{-\frac{1+s}{2}} \right) dx \quad (3)$$

From

$$\pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \zeta(s) = \int_0^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 x} x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} dx$$

and letting

$$\psi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 x} \quad x > 0$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \zeta(s) &= \int_0^{\infty} \psi(x) x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} dx \\ &= \int_0^1 \psi(x) x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} dx + \int_1^{\infty} \psi(x) x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} dx \end{aligned}$$

and since

$$\psi(x) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \psi\left(\frac{1}{x}\right),$$

$$\begin{aligned} \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \zeta(s) &= \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \psi\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) \right) x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} dx + \int_1^{\infty} \psi(x) x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{s(s-1)} + \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \psi\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) \right) x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} dx + \int_1^{\infty} \psi(x) x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} dx \end{aligned}$$

Letting $y = \frac{1}{x}$, $dy = -\frac{dx}{x^2}$

$$\pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{s(s-1)} + \int_1^{\infty} \psi(y) y^{-\frac{1+s}{2}} dy + \int_1^{\infty} \psi(x) x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} dx$$

which is *not* the same as (3). The two integrals above must be evaluated separately and can not be combined because they have different variables. Thus,

$$\pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \zeta(s) \neq \frac{1}{s(s-1)} + \int_1^{\infty} \psi(x) \left(x^{\frac{s}{2}-1} + x^{-\frac{1+s}{2}} \right) dx.$$

Therefore, (3) is also not a valid equation.

Multiplying (3) by $\frac{s(s-1)}{2}$ and setting $s = \frac{1}{2} + ti$ (which in itself is not valid because the real part of s must be greater than 1), Riemann obtained a real equation that contained the supposedly non-trivial zeros of $\zeta(s)$

$$\xi\left(\frac{1}{2} + ti\right) = \xi(t) = \frac{1}{2} - \left(t^2 + \frac{1}{4}\right) \int_1^{\infty} \psi(x) x^{-\frac{3}{4}} \cos\left(\frac{1}{2} t \ln(x)\right) dx,$$

and since (3) is an invalid equation, the above equation is also not valid. Thus, $\zeta(s)$ has *no* non-trivial zeros.

The Riemann Hypothesis(RH)

The current view of RH is that all the non-trivial zeros of $\zeta(s)$ are at $s = \frac{1}{2} + ti$. But what Riemann conjectured in his 1859 paper was about the imaginary part of s , and not its real part.

But that does not matter because $\zeta(s)$ has no zeros, $\zeta(s) \neq 0$ for all s . It was Riemann's errors that lead him and others to falsely believe that such zeros exist.

REFERENCES

[1] Riemann, Bernhard (1859). *On the Number of Prime Numbers less than a Given Magnitude*.

LINKS

- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Riemann_zeta_function
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Riemann_hypothesis